

MSO

Kitt Peak Survives Contreras Fire

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The Contreras fire, which was started by a lightning strike on 11 June 2022, grew from a small five-acre fire in the Baboquivari Mountains eight miles south of Kitt Peak National Observatory into a 30,000-acre fire that burned through the Altar Valley and Quinlan Mountains range, home to the observatory.

The fire moved rapidly, giving little time for preparation. From initial contact with the Incident Commander of the Southeast Arizona Type 3 Incident Management Team on 14 June 2022 to the complete evacuation of staff by the Incident Commander of the Eastern Area Type 2 Incident Management Team on 16 June 2022, fewer than 55 hours elapsed. During this time, a skeleton crew of essential Kitt Peak (KP) personnel worked professionally and quickly to gracefully shut down instruments and computers, cover major optics, stow flammables and caustics, move vehicles, arrange water trucks, check fire hydrants, aid fire staff, and evacuate transportable expensive assets. Firefighters on the summit worked non-stop to create areas of protection around essential buildings and domes and clear brush along the ridges, while five DC-10 (Very Large Air Tankers [VLATs]) bombarded the valleys and slopes surrounding the observatory with fire retardant.

Despite the extraordinary efforts by all the teams employing every possible precautionary tactic, by the early morning of 17 June 2022, the fire crossed the Kitt Peak access road, State Road 386 (SR 386), and burned over the Southwest Ridge. The fire then turned east and northeast toward the main summit, racing up the slopes toward the

WIYN 3.5m, SARA 0.9m, Bok 90", Spacewatch 36" and 72", and Mayall 4m telescopes and the staff dormitories and Administration building on the western side. Firefighters mounted a nearly 12-hour campaign to protect structures on the summit, followed by another 24 hours spent firefighting across the mountain.

Thanks to the valiant efforts of the firefighting crew and the emergency preparatory actions of the KP staff, no scientific structures, telescopes, or instruments were lost or damaged. Best of all, no firefighters or KP personnel were injured. However, two University of Arizona dormitories and two KP utility sheds were completely destroyed. Several buildings, including two staff dormitories, sustained major damage, and many buildings had minor damage or were impacted by smoke and ash.

The infrastructure of the observatory, however, was left in grave condition. The summit was without line power, data, or telephones. Over 20 utility poles were damaged or destroyed across the mountain. Basic services such as garbage pickup and fuel and cryogen delivery were halted. SR 386 also suffered damage. All guardrails in the last three miles were destroyed, and as monsoon rains arrived, mudslides, rockslides, and flooding became increasingly dangerous.

In the months following the fire, the observatory undertook a massive recovery effort. This was led by an Emergency Response Team composed of experts drawn from across NOIRLab and AURA. The team took a phased approach that slowly allowed increasing numbers of staff and tenants back to the

Figure 1: (Background image) Obtained with the Mayall webcam, this shows the fire encroaching on the Very Long Baseline Array antenna, Arizona Radio Observatory, and MDM on the Southwest Ridge. Overlaid images clockwise from top left: complete loss of the University of Arizona dormitory on the Southwest Ridge; significant damage to Kitt Peak staff Dormitory #3; catastrophic damage to a power pole on the Southwest Ridge; WIYN Engineer Emily Hunting working on clean-up inside WIYN after the fire; a helicopter

transporting 1 of 18 power pole replacements to areas otherwise inaccessible; an 8' x 12' x 6' boulder that fell into the access road during a storm. Erosion, due to loss of vegetation, caused multiple rockslides and mudslides along State Route 386 (SR 386) throughout the monsoon season. Fortunately, no one was injured, and the Arizona Department of

Transportation (ADOT) was able to clear the boulder from the lane, but SR 386 remains closed to the public. Credits: Background: T. "Walt" Walter/Eastern Area Type 2 Incident Management Team; Dormitories: J. Maclean (COS/NOIRLab); Electric pole: M. Edwards (KPNO/NOIRLab); E. Hunting (WIYN/KPNO/NOIRLab); S. Logsdon (WIYN/KPNO/NOIRLab); Helicopter and MMP: R. Sparks (CEE/NOIRLab); Rock and car: L. Reddell (KPNO/COS/NOIRLab)

observatory to conduct recovery and remediation efforts, only after independent assessments deemed the site free of major electrical, structural, or environmental hazards. The response team also spearheaded efforts to create and maintain direct pathways of communication with service providers and cooperators, including the Tohono O'odham Utility Authority, the Arizona Department of Transportation, and the Tohono O'odham Office of Emergency Management. These relationships helped us negotiate compromises that kept the recovery moving forward and facilitated the resolution of complex logistical challenges.

In mid-October power was restored to the main summit area. Power to the Southwest Ridge was restored by the end of November. Potable water, bathrooms, food services, and janitorial services are all restored at the time of writing (mid-September 2022). Dormitories without significant damage were thoroughly cleansed of ash and smoke, and observers and staff are back on the summit for overnight stays. Domes and telescopes were thoroughly inspected and cleaned; we are pleased to report that MDM, the University of

Arizona, Mayall, and WIYN all resumed science operations in September. Clean rooms and laboratories were also cleaned and prepared for tenant use; Caltech was able to upgrade their new instrument on-site post-fire in preparation for recommissioning on the 2.1m telescope. After a very challenging installation process, fiber internet was restored to the main summit area in early December. The Southwest Ridge is still pending internet access as this issue goes to press.

We anticipate the ongoing recovery of Kitt Peak, particularly data services, the access road, and the restart of smaller tenant telescopes and the Visitor Center, will continue throughout the next few months.

We extend our sincere thanks to all who have supported our efforts, both with fire prevention and recovery: the Arizona Department of Transportation, Tohono O'odham Office of Emergency Management, Tohono O'odham Utility Authority, NSF, Bureau of Indian Affairs, NOIRLab, Kitt Peak staff and tenants.

